

Stereotype

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Abstract

This paper seeks to further our understanding of the affective impact of lettering and typography in the environment. This research is predicated in the relationship between physical environment and semantic (in this case, typographic) codes. Two contrasting urban areas are used to elucidate the concept of visual appropriateness and meaning and are investigated in order to elucidate the theory that lettering is significant to communicating feeling, identity and social status. This research presents evidence of how feelings towards lettering in relation to place are measured. A set of visuals from each of the two environments was tested using participant groups in order to investigate the concept of semantic understanding. The results are used to present a range of findings about perception of lettering and typography in the urban environment.

Keywords: Typography, lettering, environment, semantics, urban street, semantic intention, semantic perception, cognitive, affective, individual response.

Introduction

When the city street talks, what does it say? More to the point, how does it say it? Hey! Tasty, Love, Gossip, Chic, Bargains! Lettering is so much integrated into today's environments it is difficult to imagine a properly functioning modern city without words – or images. This paper uses an empirical research method to investigate the phenomenon of lettering and perception in the environment.

As the codifying system of language, typography and lettering are key elements of modern society and form a core role in communicating and consequently understanding urban environments. Unlike the modern built environment, which is designed to be permanent or semi-permanent, the nature of lettering and typography is such that they are often semi-permanent or temporary. This lack of permanence and the fluctuating nature of commercial activity produce a constantly changing typographic environment.

Urban environments possess 'flavour', 'feeling', 'ambience', 'essence', 'resonance', 'presence', 'aura', and 'charm' (Hiss 1991). This attribution of descriptors to places is commonly used to describe the 'feel' or 'mood' of a place by architects, planners, writers and academics. When referring to the difference between the streetscapes of East and West Berlin prior to re-unification, Heller (2004) stated: '...the East Berlin modernist aesthetic legacy was a spiritual disaster'.

In open environments the aural vies with the visual for attention to create an entirely synaesthetic experience resulting in a blend of visual and audio noise. Lettering is often created to seek to project meaning and tone to the viewer. Design consultants, Lippincott Mercer (1957) discussed retail design as: 'we have tended to disregard the rich cultural roll of the market place and concentrate on the science of selling as if it were separated from people' (Lippincott Mercer, 2004). Furthermore, the professional and aesthetic aspects of environmental type have been describes as: 'the way lettering practice can contribute to a sense of place' (Baines, 2003).

In linguistic terms a word is the signifier and by convention has meaning. In design terms the visual characteristics of the word are used to convey meaning and designers regularly think in semantic terms as part of the design process (Butter, Rheinhardt, 1989) and are mindful their semantic intentions are interpreted correctly. The transient street typography of the modern urban environment presents a different perspective on the intention/perception aspect of semantic communication.

Emotional response to environments and their associated elements has been well established in psychology research (e.g. Kaplan 1987; Russell and Pratt 1980; Balling 1982). The affective qualities of environmental lighting and colour have been discussed and researched in marketing terms (Bitner 1992), and recent medical research supports the view that greenery in the urban landscape contributes to good physical health (Ellaway et al 2005).

Also, type and lettering have been considered useful chronometers of fashion (Cahalan 1999). Perception of lettering in environments is often raised when new or different contexts/surroundings are experienced (Spiekermann, 2003). Lettering in the form of signage and advertising occupies a large proportion of the modern streetscape, yet there is limited research available about its contribution to human emotion in relation to the environment.

Unambiguous information graphics in the environment, navigational and way finding graphics remove doubt and uncertainty, and introduce understanding and congruity. In this sense typography can be focused on cognitive function - like conspicuity and legibility (Zwaga et al 1999). Unlike this 'cognitive' information-oriented typography, the focus of this research project is on the environment beyond the functional and legible, and differs from research already conducted. Work to date is largely constituted by discourse related to particular aspects or genres of environmental lettering and signage. This affective impact of type and lettering in the environment forms the research core of this project.

Scope and Focus

The internationalisation of brands has located many of them in large cities across the globe -- they are the same for everyone -- worldwide. Or at least that may be part of their strategic global presence -- to standardise and commercially dominate. Feelings about these global brands are informed by a sense of brand value communicated by finely tuned marketing machines or by political/consumer attitudes to this standardisation of the high street. It can therefore be difficult to disentangle emotional response to these signs from the cultural noise surrounding them. Muji, Starbucks, Virgin, and Zara exist in many city centres, Europe-wide, and so the identities of arterial routes or districts have in themselves developed their own visual character -- taking on a bespoke visual language. They are often governed by local demographics or focused targeting of specific or local audiences/consumers. Similarly, they may have been located on a particular site because of some historic reason and are often punctuated by large national and international brands (local hardware stores/Texaco/local

newsagent). Due to their uniqueness and individual nature they tend to be free from the attendant media baggage associated with well known brands that might lead to pre-judgment and qualification these local examples provide a good source for research.

This paper compares and contrasts two very different commercial districts of Belfast -the Lisburn Road (Lisburn) and the Shore Road (Shore). Lisburn has a high concentration of prestigious clothing and lifestyle retailers alongside numerous cafés, restaurants and wine bars. Shore is characterised by fast food outlets, low price retailers, vacant shops and traditional pubs and clubs. Both are arterial routes that share similar architectural vernacular features – period, materials and elevation.

Of interest is the key role of typography and lettering in communicating the character of a place, and the role lettering plays in perceptions of public space. Existing conceptual models for discussing the emotional perception of products exist (Desmet and Heckert 2002, Ortony et al 1998). These models propose a product to have three major aspects related to emotional perception: product as object, product as agent and product as event. They provide a useful mapping exercise for this discussion of the emotional perception of environmental typography. The lettering in the study may be disliked but acknowledged as appropriate and therefore effective, the function of type is to raise consciousness of the product or service and alert the viewer to the location. The semantic agency of lettering in this circumstance is core to the research. Respondents may have an attitude of liking or disliking influenced by the physical manifestation; colour, materials used, composition, choice of font however perception is intimately entwined with the word/s and factors like; literary references (e.g. Swallows and Amazons), contemporary use (e.g. Kandi), assumed cultural knowledge (e.g. French cuisine terms).

Method and Protocols

Visuals are used in order to generate descriptors from participant groups and to measure various aspects of visual perception. A range of ten images from each of the two locations depicting lettering in context were used as stimuli. The selected ten images were chosen because they conveyed a range of individual premises that collectively contributed to the environment and provided an accurate representation of each of the localities. Participant groups were specifically briefed to assess the visual qualities of the lettering/typography. While these were presented within their environments as photographic images, participants

were urged to treat the visual context as secondary information. Each experiment session lasted approximately 40 minutes.

Photographs were used in order to eliminate other experiential factors (sound, smell weather) not under direct consideration. Some of the most important research into the semantic properties of typography has occurred in 'ideal' standardised conditions (Bartram,1982). However central to this investigation is the notion of the contextual experience of typography. The Shannon and Weaver model of communication (1963), often adapted for design thinking, (Monö,1997) positions design perception as a transmission–signal–receiver process where noise (interference, distraction) can effect the efficiency of the signal.

As a consequence the visual examples were shown exactly as photographed, no image manipulation was used, no isolation of the lettering was attempted and any consideration of standardised representation was rejected.

When considering the possibility that environmental typographic forms communicate meaning in addition to information, it was considered important that descriptors were generated directly by the sample groups - free from contextualisation or comparison. It was hoped that some inference might be drawn from the differences between the groups generating and articulating emotive responses and the groups assigning them to an abstract concept.

Under standard experiment conditions, a group of 25 year one design students were asked to look at a series of ten images from Lisburn. No prior knowledge of the locations or images was assumed. The sample group were asked to pay particular attention to the lettering and signage in the images and to provide a short written individual and anonymous response to each image detailing their feelings about the subject. It was assumed they had a reasonable level of visual literacy and were required to use their own words. No information about the location or contextual information was given, and there was no contrast and comparison element. As year one students they were not yet accustomed to discussing the semantic characteristics of design artefacts.

The exercise was repeated with a different sample group of 25 year one design students and an unconnected series of images from Shore were shown. At the end of the first stage of the

experiment fifty individual generated response sheets were produced for the two sets of images.

The next stage of the experiment involved analysing written responses and isolating the descriptive words used by student sample groups. In order to explore the full scope of feelings to the subject, all descriptions, affective and cognitive were analysed at this point.

In total the Shore images generated 374 adjectives from 10 images and the Lisburn images had generated 573 adjectives from 10 images.

From the combined total of 947 adjectives a list of 207 distinct adjectives used in the descriptions were extracted by eliminating the repeated words. These adjectives were randomly placed into four columns on a single A4 sheet and used as the basis for a second round of sample responses. This was done in order to present the key words generated from part one of the experiment and to look at the perceived relationships between generated and ascribed descriptors.

In the second round of sample responses a completely new set of students, drawn from a different though similar course, was used as a sample group. They were asked to spend ten minutes familiarising themselves with the prepared list of adjectives resulting from stage one. The sample group were then shown the first series of ten images (Shore) and asked to assign words only from the supplied list that best matched their feelings towards the lettering depicted in the photographs. As in the first stage of the experiment a second group of students were asked to look at the second series of images (Lisburn) and assign what they felt to be those adjectives that most closely reflected their feelings, thus avoiding any comparison or relativity. Two groups of ten students yielded twenty individual response sheets.

Initial analysis

In the first round of data collection, respondents were encouraged to write freely about their feelings concerning the lettering as shown in environmental context. From these responses, the adjective words were extracted. The 374 adjectives generated from the Shore Road images produced 122 negative, 108 neutral and 144 positive responses. Lisburn Road images generated a total of 573 adjectives from 10 images - 71 negative, 35 neutral and 466 positive.

Although some preferences may have been anticipated there was a noticeable divergence in the expression of feeling to both sets of images. (See Fig.1)

Fig.1 Generated responses to Shore Road and Lisburn Road image sets.

Lisburn results indicate a considerably higher number of positive descriptors and show a greater propensity to generate positive descriptors. Contrastingly, Shore images failed to show any significant difference between negative, neutral and positive feelings – resulting in a ‘flatline’ perception.

In part two of the experiment, respondents were required to use the previously generated list of adjective descriptors to express feelings concerning the lettering as shown in environmental context. Shore images were assigned a total of 459 adjectives (308 negative, 72 neutral and 79 positive). Lisburn images were assigned a total of 495 (95 negative, 21 neutral and 379 positive). (See Fig.2)

Fig.2 Assigned responses to Shore Road and Lisburn Road image sets.

The assigned response (Fig 2.) shows a clear difference in the assignment of positive and negative descriptors to the two locations. This clearly shows a correlation between positive descriptors and an upmarket location and negative descriptors and a downmarket location.

This data demonstrates less of a proclivity to generate negative descriptors in the initial sample group. When given the verbal toolkit in the form of a list of previously generated adjectives, the assigned responses from the second sample group appear to accentuate the negative aspects of the downmarket location resulting in two profiles that appear to mirror each other, (Fig.2.) This apparent difference in generated and assigned negative and positive descriptors for the two locations is further illustrated in Fig.3 and Fig.4.

Fig.3 Shore

Fig.4 Lisburn

In this initial analysis all generated and assigned adjectives have been included in the data. It has already been noted that there were 50% more adjectives generated for Lisburn, (573) than Shore (374). Lisburn generated many more positive adjectives of a wider variety. It was also apparent from the responses that the majority of adjectives could best be described as cognitive. Of the 207 different adjectives generated by both groups, 30 adjectives were considered as positive affective descriptors, 18 negative (affective descriptors) and 159 cognitive descriptors. Those adjectives generated on multiple occasions were cognitive or neutral, such as ‘bold’, ‘conspicuous’, ‘clear’, ‘straight-forward’, ‘jumbled, and eye-catching’. In order to further tease out aspects of affective feeling in the data, it was decided to isolate those words that were most clearly affective (‘aggressive’, ‘boring’, ‘nice’, ‘inviting’, ‘delightful’, ‘terrible’, ‘pleasant’, ‘unappealing’) from the generated and assigned responses. There was a marked difference in affective descriptor use between the two locations. 35% of the generated adjective use for the Shore Road was affective; of the assigned adjective use for the Shore Road, 32% was considered affective. The Lisburn Road generated, and was assigned, markedly fewer affective adjectives: 11% and 13% respectively.

The incidence of generated or assigned affective response is shown in fig.5 and fig.6. Of interest is the relative high use of affective descriptors for visuals related to the socially disadvantaged Shore responses compared with those assigned to the relatively affluent Lisburn images. It is unclear as to why there should be higher incidence of the more emotive (positive or negative) adjectives assigned to the Shore when compared to the Lisburn.

Fig.5 Assigned affective adjectives for Shore.

Fig.6 Assigned affective adjectives for Lisburn Road.

The two-stage approach enables singularly defined responses to be mapped against more narrative descriptions. This is of particular interest in the analysis of letterform usage in relation to place and environments and how they can be perceived as being in actual or conceptual harmony (schema congruity) with the viewer or how they contribute to notion of visual or conceptual confrontation, threat, and disarray.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to investigate the role of emotive response to typographic and letterform communication in the urban landscape. It was limited by the demography of the sample group and any inferences from the data would require further testing with sample groups from a wider age range and variety of backgrounds. The sample groups were presumed to be somewhat visually literate but without any particular typographic background. The primary evidence available from these tests would appear to advance the concept that people do have an emotional reaction to environmental type and lettering and that these emotional responses may not be obvious or anticipated.

The differences between perceived descriptive qualities and assigned descriptive qualities noted in Figs.1 and 2 raises questions concerning the formulation and articulation of responses to typographic and lettering forms and affords further opportunity for research into applied evaluative methods. It is significant that when supplied with a previously generated list of adjectives, respondents were noticeably more inclined to use negative descriptions. Similarly the differences in the use of affective adjectives for Shore raise questions about the extent of emotive response to negative (or positive) perceptions of typographic communication in the environment.

This study indicates that typographic communication in the built environment plays a contributory role in the sum of feelings concerning our immediate surroundings. The cumulative or holistic sense of place provided by a series of examples reflects a truer picture of the actual experience of the urban environment and the significant differences between the two locations in relation to lettering and type cannot be easily explained. There are notable differences in terms of approach to materials, colour and composition and many of the apparently positive cognitive responses, such as chic, understated, stylish and contemporary generated for Lisburn (prosperous) seem to contribute to an overall positive emotional

response. Investment of time and effort in the conception and execution of signs rather than any obvious cost difference in manufacture appears to contribute to subsequent interpretation.

Commercially, type and lettering are used to differentiate locations for business, social and cultural purposes and to attract our attention away from other environmental factors. This study confirms that type and lettering also contribute to emotional navigation, differentiation and attraction to the environment.

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Appendix

Shore Road, Men's Barber

Shore Road, Fast Food

Shore Road, Petrol Station

Lisburn Road, Hairdresser

Lisburn Road, Sandwich Shop

Lisburn Road, Petrol Station

The adjectives and descriptors generated by the sample groups.

Bold	Not easy on eye	Plain	Innocent
Clear	Eye catching colour	Simple	Smooth
Precise	Bright	Boring/Dull	Unclear
Understated	Too bold/structured	Bold	Familiar
Complimentary	Short	Doesn't communicate	Friendly
Professional	Sharp	Abandoned	Valiant
Minimalist/simple	Fresh	Dated	Masculine
Pleasing	Dark	Appropriate	
Modern		Inappropriate	Old
	Pleasant		Classy
Contemporary	Horrible	Clear contrast	Washed out
Clean cut	Relaxing	Low Quality	Retro
Official	Familiar	Poor Grammar	60's
Serious	Decorative	Cheap	Unusual
Expensive	Playful	Unappealing	
Elegant	Clashing	Not pleasing	Alone
Neutral	Stark	Functional	Jagged
	Thick	Sad	Classic
Formal			Authentic
Upmarket	Feminine	Lonely	Chic
Quality	Unsuitable	Gross	Futuristic
Stylish	Country	Worn	Spacey
Sophisticated	Smooth	Victorian	Kitsch
Subtle	Flowy	Standard	Swirly
neat	Fun	Uninteresting	Cosy
	Light-hearted	Factual	
		Striking	
Old Style	Easy	Conspicuous	Mish-Mash
Basic	Legible	Cheerful	Chaos
Fine	Soft	Complimentary	Amateur
Small	Chunky	Attractive	Terrible
Nice	Welcoming	Vivid	Confusing
Bland	Dirty	Vibrant	Erratic
Aggressive	Grand	Effective	Illegible
Jaunty	Personal	Tacky	Worn
Unremarkable	Signature	Unattractive	Dirty
Barren	Quality	Uncompromising	Messy
Traditional	Posh	Carefree	Irregular
Sexy		Whimsical	Conflicting
Childish	Sleek	Upmarket	Cluttered
Clever	Stable	Expensive	Ornate
Funky	No-nonsense	Low key	Celtic
Quirky	Decisive	Casual	Fluid
Loose	Commercial	Cliché	Calligraphic
Stereotypical	Functional	Elegant	Acid
Adventurous	Prominent	Tidy	Folky
Inviting	Direct	Cute	Intricate
Wishy-Washy	Knowledgeable	Concise	Handcrafted
Neon	Squat	Asymmetrical	Ye Olde
Technological	Metric	Trendy	Homely
Stylish	Neat	Shy	Comfortable
New Age	Fashionable	Quiet	Cultural
Delightful	Different	Modest	Established
Flimsy	Mysterious	Fancy	Swishy
Slanty		Artistic	Laid Back
Elaborate		French	

Affective adjectives and descriptors

Pleasing	Innocent
Dull	Bland
Terrible	Familiar
Fresh	Friendly
Pleasant	Valiant
Relaxing	Horrible
Familiar	Alone
Playful	Nice
Fun	Aggressive
Light-hearted	Sexy
Boring	Easy
Abandoned	Welcoming
Unappealing	Carefree
Not pleasing	Whimsical
Sad	Cheerful
Lonely	Attractive
Gross	Vibrant
Uninteresting	Tacky
Delightful	Unattractive
Cosy	Confusing
Mysterious	Childish
Cute	Inviting
Shy	Laid Back
Comfortable	